

PLEP-0003 – Members of Coordinating Committee

PlasmaPy Community

PLEP	3
author(s)	PlasmaPy Community
date created	2017-09-29
date last revised	2018-09-26
type	informational

Abstract

This document lists the membership of the PlasmaPy Coordinating Committee.

Coordinating Committee Membership

The PlasmaPy Coordinating Committee includes the following members:

Name	Institution	GitHub nickname
Drew Leonard	Aperio Software	@SolarDrew
Nicholas Murphy	Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics	@namurphy
Tulasi Parashar	University of Delaware	@tulasinandan
Dominik Stańczak	University of Warsaw	@StanczakDominik

The institutions of Coordinating Committee members are included for identification purposes only.